

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LITERARY LANGUAGE AND DIALECTS

Qurbanova Asal O'tkirovna

1st year student of the Department of Philology and Language Teaching (Uzbek) at Karshi International University.

For inquiries, please contact: Tel: (77) 314-21-17.

Gmail: qurbanovaasal979@gmail.com

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Abstract. *The article provides a deep analysis of the relationship between literary languages and dialects, their linguistic and speech interaction. From a scientific and theoretical point of view, the role of the literary language in society, the stages of its formation and development, as well as the influence of dialects on the literary language and their place in the structure of the national language are covered. The use of literary languages and dialects in literary works, the significance of dialects in the process of language development and their place as a linguistic phenomenon are also considered. Based on linguistic research, the article also studies the historical, social and cultural aspects of literary languages and dialects, analyzes their mutual agreement and differences.*

Keywords: *literary language, dialect, national language, linguistic phenomenon, speech phenomenon, language of a work of art, dialect, linguistics, communication, language development, phonetic changes, morphological features, syntactic construction, sociolinguistics, cultural influence, language units, terminology, regional identity.*

СВЯЗЬ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОГО ЯЗЫКА С ДИАЛЕКТАМИ

Аннотация. *В статье дается глубокий анализ взаимосвязи литературных языков и диалектов, их языкового и речевого взаимодействия. С научно-теоретической точки зрения освещаются роль литературного языка в обществе, этапы его становления и развития, а также влияние диалектов на литературный язык и их место в структуре национального языка. Также рассматриваются использование литературных языков и диалектов в литературных произведениях, значение диалектов в процессе развития языка и их место как языкового явления. На основе лингвистических исследований в статье также изучаются исторические, социальные и культурные аспекты литературных языков и диалектов, анализируется их взаимное согласие и различия.*

Ключевые слова: *литературный язык, диалект, национальный язык, языковой феномен, речевой феномен, язык художественного произведения, диалект, лингвистика, коммуникация, развитие языка, фонетические изменения, морфологические признаки, синтаксическое построение, социолингвистика, культурное влияние, языковые единицы, терминология, региональная идентичность.*

Introduction

The literary language plays a crucial role in the cultural and scientific development of any nation. It serves as a primary means of communication, defining the intellectual level of society and being widely used in science, education, media, governance, and daily communication. As a reflection of a nation's unique identity, the literary language continuously evolves and enriches itself through various linguistic influences. Dialects play an essential role in the development of a language.

They serve as a significant linguistic source for the formation and evolution of the literary language. Dialects represent natural speech variations found in specific regions or communities, characterized by unique phonetic, lexical, and grammatical features. The interaction between dialects and the literary language helps enrich the language, incorporating new words and expressions. At the same time, the literary language standardizes and regulates dialectal elements, ensuring a unified mode of communication. This article explores the relationship between literary language and dialects, examining their linguistic and communicative aspects, the role of dialects in the development of the literary language, and their social and cultural significance from a theoretical perspective.

Main Part

Literary language is a processed and standardized form of a certain national language, serving the cultural needs of the people speaking this language. The concept of “reprocessed” is relative (historically, the literary language has changed in different periods and among different peoples). Even for some people, the literary language was different at different times (for example, the ancient Turkic literary language, the current Uzbek literary language). In some periods, another national language served as a literary language for one people. For example, classical Arabic for the Persians and Turks, classical Chinese for the Japanese; Latin for some European peoples, etc.

There are two forms of literary language - oral and written. Any literary language is formed on the basis of folk oral speech, generalizes the dialects characteristic of this national language, and takes on a form understandable to all representatives of the dialect. Without a developed literary language, there cannot be a people with a rich culture. In this sense, literary language is one of the urgent problems of society. When we say literary language, we sometimes confuse it with its various manifestations. In particular, written literary language and oral literary language, as well as the language of fiction, cannot be considered the same. Literary language, which has its own criteria, is the same for all speakers of this language. It is used in practice in both written and oral forms. Although the language of a literary work also obeys the norms of the literary language, it embodies many peculiarities and aspects that are not generally recognized. In different peoples, at all times, the literary language and the language of a literary work have not been identical.

There is also a difference between a literary language and a national language. A national language arises when the people who own this language form a nation. A national language serves as a literary language, but not every literary language can immediately become a national language.

The relationship between literary language and dialects is a separate issue. How historically dialects have developed the more stable the dialects are, the more difficult it is to generalize the representatives of dialects for the literary language from a linguistic point of view. Nowadays, in many countries (for example, Italy, Indonesia, etc.), dialects are used on an equal footing with the literary language. The concept of literary language is usually associated with the concept of language styles. However, this connection is one-sided. Because language styles themselves are manifestations of the literary language. They consist of a set of historically formed, specific signs.

Some of these signs can be repeated in other styles. However, the combination of these repeated signs in a certain way and the specificity of their function determine the difference between one style and another. The granting of the status of the State Language to the Uzbek language (1989) was an important event that ensured the development of the Uzbek literary language.

The Uzbek literary language is developing further based on the experience of developing the literary languages of different peoples. Today, there is no clear definition of the concept of “language” in linguistics. The reason for this is that language is understood differently in different nations, in different countries, and among people in general, the boundaries of languages accepted in world linguistics are determined on the basis of different criteria and are not based on clear scientific factors. Most linguists today consider language to be a political phenomenon. That is, a particular language is formed within certain political boundaries, and its difference from neighboring languages and dialects is not biological, but political. The American Germanist Max Weinreich was the first to jokingly say this at the 19th International Conference of the Jewish Scientific Institute in New York in 1945. “Language is a dialect with an army and a fleet,” he said.

This definition of his is still remembered today. Therefore, in some countries, a collection of dialects that have become very distant from each other and have become mutually incomprehensible is considered a single language, while in some places, on the contrary, languages that do not differ from each other are considered separate languages. This situation has given rise to the “language - dialect” problem in linguistics. That is, there is no clear boundary between language and dialect, no clear scientific criteria distinguishing them. National (universal) language, literary language and dialects The language used by all people of the Uzbek nationality, regardless of where they live, is called the national (universal) Uzbek language. The national language includes such groups of words as dialect, colloquial speech, jargon, vulgarisms (swearing, cursing words), barbarisms (foreign words used inappropriately in the language).

The form of the national language, which is subject to certain rules, molded into a certain mold, processed by scientists, artists, specialists, and constantly polished and perfected, is called the literary language. The need for the literary language to be understandable to all speakers of this language led to the creation of the literary language. The large number of dialects in the national Uzbek language has created a need for a literary language. In some languages (for example, Finnish), there is no need for a literary language due to the small number of dialects. Official documents, artistic and scientific literature, periodical press are created in the literary language, the mass media work in the literary language. A dialect is a national language form used by people belonging to the same nationality but living in different regions. A dialect differs from the literary language in phonetic (i.e. sound), lexical (i.e. word) and grammatical (i.e. suffixes and sentence structure) aspects. Folk dialects have only an oral form. Groups of dialects that are close to each other are called dialects (the word dialect expresses the concepts of dialect and dialect together).

The Uzbek national language includes three dialects: the Qarluq dialect (south-eastern group). the Kipchak dialect (south-western group). the Oghuz dialect (north-western group). the Qarluq dialect mainly includes urban dialects (Tashkent, Andijan, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Karshi). The important phonetic and morphological features of these dialects are as follows: the sound k at the end of a word is pronounced as y: elak - elay, terak - teray; o-spelling occurs: aka - oka, nahor - nahor; in this dialect, the accusative case suffix -ni is absent, and the accusative case suffix -ni is used instead: ukamni(ng) daftari. Dialects of the Kipchak dialect are found in all regions of Uzbekistan, they are mainly distributed in villages (Samarkand, Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, Karakalpakstan, Northern Khorezm regions, dialects of the Toshavuz region of Turkmenistan). The signs are as follows: instead of y, j is used: yo'l - jo'l, yo'k - jo'q; instead of g', v is used: tog' - tov, sog' - sov, etc.; k, q are dropped: kuri(q), sari(q). The Oghuz dialect includes several dialects in Southern Khorezm (Urgench, Khiva, Khanka, Hazorasp, Qoshko'pir, Shovat districts).

Signs: vowels are pronounced short and long: at (animal), aad (noun); the sound t is pronounced d, and k is pronounced g: tog' - dog', keldi - galdi; the suffix -ning is pronounced -ing, and the suffix -ga is pronounced -a, -na: yorimga - yorimga. The Fergana-Tashkent dialects, which are part of the Karluk dialect, were used as the basis for the current Uzbek literary language.

According to scientists, the Tashkent dialect is the phonetic basis of the literary language, and the Fergana dialect is morphologically the basis. In general, the literary language is based on all dialects. The specific features of dialects gradually weaken and disappear under the influence of the literary language. Words and grammatical forms in the colloquial language are units that are used in all dialects, but are formed differently from the literary language: kelsa - kesa, bolsa - bo'sa, olib kel - opkel. Vulgarisms are swear words and curses that exist in the language: haromi, qiztalaq, yer yutkur, aqpadar, etc.

Barbarisms are foreign words used inappropriately in the language: I couldn't succeed, papasha, mamasha, nastroeniem yashchi, znachit, tak, wow, yess, etc. Jargonisms are words with a hidden meaning used by certain groups of people: mullajiring, loy soqqa, kurugi (all in the sense of money).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the literary language and dialects are closely related. We think that studying them as a separate direction is a mistake. Because the literary language is also enriched and saturated with dialects. In the early 1920s, a scientist who spoke at the Language and Spelling Congress held in our republic approached the issue as follows: "The richness of vocabulary, breadth of interest, completeness of rules, and pearls of grammar in our language are not inferior to other oriental languages. In this regard, it completely leaves Persian behind."

Abdurauf Fitrat fought for the purity and richness of his language without denigrating other languages. The literary language is important for studying dialects, because it is necessary to know the equivalent of a word in the literary language. After understanding the meaning of a word, it is studied by comparing it with its equivalent in the dialect. Barbarisms and vulgarisms also play a large role in the study of literary languages and dialects. Because they are one of the factors that create and increase the effectiveness of both written and oral speech. Therefore, they are inseparable concepts.

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